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**Flexible pricing strategies and length of stay management during high
demand volatility**

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Abstract. The complexity of the operating conditions of hospitality enterprises, caused by changes in demand, intensification of competitive processes, and transformation of customer preferences, requires hospitality enterprises to implement adaptive management tools capable of ensuring a balance between revenue maximization and the rational use of available resources. The **purpose of the article** is to analyze and substantiate practical approaches to flexible pricing and length-of-stay management that increase the financial performance of hospitality businesses in conditions of high demand volatility. **Methods.** To achieve the set goal, a set of theoretical methods of scientific knowledge was used, in particular, analysis and synthesis to generalize scientific approaches, abstraction to identify key characteristics of demand volatility, and induction and deduction to form conclusions and practical recommendations. **Results.** Key factors influencing the volatility of demand in the national and regional hotel services markets include economic conditions, consumer socio-psychological expectations, seasonality, event activity, and price and competitive factors. It has been proven that effective demand management involves not only prompt tariff adjustments but also targeted

regulation of the length of stay based on market dynamics, customer segment, and room stock occupancy. Analysis of modern pricing approaches, in particular dynamic pricing, market penetration strategies, and prestige pricing, enabled assessment of their effectiveness across consumer segments during periods of sharp demand fluctuations. Based on the results obtained, practical recommendations have been formulated for implementing integrated, flexible strategies that combine the automation of reservation management systems, segmental differentiation of tariffs, and the establishment of adaptive restrictions on the minimum and maximum length of stay. **Conclusions.** The use of adaptive pricing mechanisms, segmental demand management, and regulation of stay parameters ensures increased profitability, higher occupancy levels, and reduced risk of profit shortfalls, which together strengthen the competitiveness and financial stability of hospitality enterprises in a changing market environment.

Keywords: length of stay management, hospitality enterprises, adaptive management, economic factors, market strategies, reservation automation, competitiveness.

Гнучкі стратегії ціноутворення і керування тривалістю проживання під час високої волатильності попиту

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Анотація. Ускладнення умов функціонування підприємств сфери гостинності, спричинене зміною попиту, інтенсифікацією конкурентних процесів та трансформацією споживчих уподобань клієнтів, вимагає від підприємств гостинності впровадження адаптивних управлінських інструментів, здатних забезпечити баланс між максимізацією доходів і

раціональним використанням наявних ресурсів. **Метою роботи** є аналіз та обґрунтування ефективних підходів до гнучкого ціноутворення й управління тривалістю перебування, які сприяють підвищенню фінансової результативності бізнесу у сфері гостинності в умовах високої волатильності попиту. **Методи.** Для досягнення поставленої мети використано комплекс теоретичних методів наукового пізнання, зокрема аналіз і синтез – для узагальнення наукових підходів, абстрагування – для виокремлення ключових характеристик волатильності попиту, а також індукцію та дедукцію – для формування висновків і практичних рекомендацій. **Результати.** Визначено ключові фактори, що впливають на волатильність попиту на національному та регіональних ринках готельних послуг, зокрема, економічні умови, соціально-психологічні очікування споживачів, сезонність, подієва активність, а також цінові й конкурентні чинники. Доведено, що ефективне управління попитом передбачає не лише оперативне коригування тарифів, а й цілеспрямоване регулювання тривалості перебування залежно від динаміки ринку, сегмента клієнтів і завантаженості номерного фонду. Аналіз сучасних цінових підходів, зокрема динамічного ціноутворення, стратегій проникнення на ринок та престижного ціноутворення, дозволив оцінити їхню ефективність у різних споживчих сегментах у періоди різких коливань попиту. На основі отриманих результатів сформульовано практичні рекомендації щодо впровадження інтегрованих гнучких стратегій, які поєднують автоматизацію систем управління бронюванням, сегментну диференціацію тарифів та встановлення адаптивних обмежень щодо мінімальної і максимальної тривалості проживання. **Висновки.** Застосування адаптивних механізмів ціноутворення, сегментного управління попитом і регулювання параметрів перебування забезпечує зростання доходності, підвищення рівня завантаженості та зменшення ризиків недоотримання прибутку, що в сукупності сприяє зміцненню конкурентоспроможності та фінансової стійкості підприємств гостинності в умовах мінливої ринкової кон'юнктури.

Ключові слова: управління тривалістю перебування, підприємства гостинності, адаптивне управління, економічні чинники, ринкові стратегії, автоматизація бронювання, конкурентоспроможність.

Problem statement. In the modern hospitality industry, flexible pricing strategies and length-of-stay management are essential tools for ensuring the competitiveness of hotels and other accommodation establishments. High volatility of demand, caused by economic fluctuations, transformation of consumer preferences, as well as the influence of external shocks, in particular pandemics and geopolitical crises, in the hospitality sector, reveals the limitations of traditional approaches to tariff formation. This highlights the need to implement adaptive pricing strategies that not only account for market price dynamics but also ensure more effective coordination of supply with actual demand during different periods of establishment occupancy.

At the same time, the insufficient integration of modern digital technologies, in particular big data analytics tools and artificial intelligence algorithms, into the practice of revenue management in hotel enterprises limits their ability to increase the accuracy of management decisions. As a result, demand forecasting and the development of optimal pricing solutions remain insufficiently justified, leading to financial losses for business entities and negatively affecting consumer satisfaction with hotel services. In addition, the lack of a systematic analysis of socio-economic and behavioral factors complicates the development of management and marketing strategies for hospitality establishments that can flexibly account for the characteristics of individual market segments and consumer types.

The relevance of the study is determined by the need for prompt adaptation of hospitality enterprises to dynamic changes in the market environment, driven by globalization and the digitalization of the economy. For hotel business entities, this involves reviewing traditional approaches to pricing and implementing scientifically based mechanisms for managing the length of stay as part of the revenue

management system, which help reduce financial risks, increase the efficient use of the room fund, and ensure the stability of economic results.

Thus, the study of flexible pricing strategies and length-of-stay management during periods of high demand volatility is crucial for the development of management theory and practice in the hospitality industry. The results of such research will contribute to the creation of business models that can effectively withstand the challenges of the modern market and ensure the long-term sustainability of enterprises.

Analysis of recent research and publications. High demand variability in the hotel business makes the study of adaptive pricing strategies and approaches to length-of-stay management relevant. The reason for this is the inability of traditional methods for setting tariffs and planning room occupancy to ensure sufficient efficiency in revenue management in a volatile market.

Scientist O. Lysenko shows that large hotel chains, in particular Hilton, use unified corporate pricing strategies that, in operational activities, are transformed into situationally dynamic approaches that take into account seasonality of demand, booking periods, and local market characteristics. At the same time, the author emphasizes that the lack of comprehensive predictive modeling of demand and revenues limits their growth potential and reduces the validity of management decisions in the revenue management system [1]. In this context, M. Riabenka emphasizes the need for systematic consideration of internal factors of the functioning of hotel enterprises (occupancy level, room stock structure, cost component) and external parameters of the market environment (economic conditions, competitive situation, consumer behavior), as well as the integration of modern information technologies into the processes of making management decisions by hotel enterprise management in the field of pricing and length of stay management. Such an approach, in the author's opinion, lays the groundwork for the transition of hotel business entities to more flexible, scientifically based revenue management models in conditions of high demand volatility [2].

The study by L. Lima Santos, C. Gomes, C. Malheiros, C. Crespo, C. Bento shows that during periods of crisis, the financial sustainability of hotels is primarily ensured by flexible tariff policies and price differentiation, while the insufficient use of length of stay control, package offers and loyalty programs limits the possibilities of maximizing revenue, especially in independent hotels, which indicates a gap in the application of comprehensive revenue management strategies [3]. The results of the studies by M. Krytskyi [4] and V. Levit [5] convincingly indicate that implementing innovative and sustainable approaches in the business processes of service enterprises creates the prerequisites for the formation of long-term competitive advantages. At the same time, in scientific publications and management practice, these approaches are mainly analyzed at the general sectoral level, without sufficient adaptation to the specifics of hotel business operations, where the consistency of pricing strategies with demand management mechanisms and consumer behavior becomes crucial. The need to deepen such approaches in an applied dimension is confirmed by the studies of V. Ivankov, A. Chukhlib, S. Stender, G. Azarenkov, I. Nazarenko [6] and Y. Hrushko [7], which substantiate the role of digital transformation in enterprise revenue management. The authors prove that the use of innovative technologies, digital tools and personalized algorithms provides a prompter response to demand fluctuations, increases the accuracy of pricing processes and contributes to the formation of sustainable customer loyalty in an unstable market environment. An important addition to this scientific discourse is the position of Y. Hrushko [8], which emphasizes that the effectiveness of modern communication strategies in the countries of the European Union is determined not so much by the set of tools as by the level of cultural adjustment and the consistency of communication messages with local characteristics of perception. I. V. Labazevych and N. S. Kosar [9] indicate the need for careful consideration of pricing strategies and seasonality to create the prerequisites for the formation of more stable interaction models. At the same time, the research of S. V. Kovalchuk focuses on the conditions of the Ukrainian market,

emphasizing the influence of war, seasonality and structural transformations on the need to implement flexible pricing strategies and synchro marketing solutions to maintain competitiveness and investment attractiveness [10].

Highlighting previously unresolved parts of the general problem.

Analysis of scientific publications indicates significant attention among researchers to issues of pricing, revenue management, and workload optimization in the hospitality sector. The works of domestic and foreign authors examine individual aspects of dynamic pricing, the use of revenue management systems, and the influence of seasonality and consumer behavioral characteristics on demand formation. At the same time, within the existing research framework, the issue of length-of-stay management is analyzed chiefly in a fragmented manner, as an auxiliary tool of tariff policy, without a careful consideration of its relationship with flexible pricing strategies in conditions of high demand volatility. The integration of modern digital technologies and analytical methods into pricing and length-of-stay management processes has not been sufficiently studied, thereby limiting hotel enterprises' ability to adapt quickly to market changes. There is also a lack of empirical research assessing the effectiveness of specific pricing strategies and length-of-stay restrictions across different segments of the hotel services market. This necessitates further scientific research into the above management tools to build effective business strategies in the modern hospitality market.

Formulation of the article objectives (task statement). The purpose of the article is to study and substantiate flexible pricing strategies and length of stay management in conditions of high demand volatility in order to maximize revenues and effectively use the resources of a hospitality enterprise.

Tasks of the article:

1. To analyze the factors affecting demand fluctuations and their impact on the formation of flexible pricing strategies and length of stay.
2. To study pricing strategies and tools for adaptive management of minimum and maximum length of stay.

3. To develop practical recommendations for the implementation of flexible pricing strategies and length of stay management to increase the competitiveness and financial stability of hotel business enterprises.

Presentation of the primary material of the study. Demand volatility manifests as rapid, difficult-to-predict changes in consumer demand for goods and services driven by economic, social, seasonal, and regulatory factors. It characterizes the instability of consumer needs and behavioral responses to fluctuations in the market environment, which significantly complicates forecasting and necessitates flexible, adaptive pricing and resource management approaches by enterprises [11]. Demand volatility is an indicator of market unpredictability that directly affects strategic planning, financial stability, and the competitiveness of enterprises. In a dynamic and unstable market environment, the activities of hospitality enterprises depend on constant changes in consumer behavior, fluctuations in seasonal demand and the influence of external factors. To effectively manage flexible pricing strategies and length-of-stay in the face of significant demand fluctuations, it is essential to understand which factors drive demand and how they affect enterprise business processes in the hotel sector. Table 1 systematizes the key categories of factors and the nature of their influence on the dynamics of demand in the hospitality sector.

Table 1

Factors of consumer demand formation in the hotel business

Category	Factors	Impact on demand dynamics and economic consequences for hotel business enterprises
Macroeconomic	Income level of the population	Increasing income of the population increases the demand for hotel services among the middle and premium segments; customers' willingness to pay higher rates increases
	Inflation	Increasing the general price level reduces the purchasing power of consumers, which leads to a decrease in demand for services among budget categories; this requires adjustment of tariffs and promotions
	Economic policy (taxes, rates)	Changes in tax and financial policy affect customer spending and operating expenses of enterprises, which require adjustment of pricing strategies

Category	Factors	Impact on demand dynamics and economic consequences for hotel business enterprises
	State of the economy	Positive or negative expectations of consumers regarding economic development determine the willingness to book hotel services; demand fluctuations require dynamic tariff management
Social and psychological	Consumer tastes and fashion	New trends (e.g., the popularity of eco-hotels or digital services) direct demand to new segments, forcing companies to adapt service packages and tariffs
	Psychological state of the market	The dominance of panic or euphoria among consumers changes the pace of bookings and service refusals; it requires prompt adjustment of prices and minimum/maximum stay policies
	Demographic changes	The growth or decline of specific age groups (e.g., the increase in young tourists) changes the structure of demand, which affects tariff segmentation and marketing campaigns
Specific	Seasonality	Increased demand during holiday and tourist periods leads to the need for tariff differentiation and restrictions on the minimum length of stay
	Geopolitical	Conflicts, travel restrictions or travel reduce demand for hotel services; require real-time adaptation of rates and promotions
	Technological innovations	The introduction of new services or digital platforms changes customer expectations and can stimulate demand for additional services; new products need to be integrated into pricing models
	Regulatory changes	New laws, safety standards or tax changes affect business costs and the final cost of services; require a review of pricing policy
Market and price	Prices of related goods	Increasing prices for alternative or complementary services (transport, entertainment) change the demand for hotel services; this requires adjustment of rates and package offers
	Asset liquidity	Availability of rooms and additional services determines sales volume; lack of resources can limit demand even with high customer interest
	Supply and demand balance	Excess supply reduces prices and stimulates promotions; shortage increases rates and length of stay requirements; and directly affects revenues and operational efficiency

Source: created by the author based on [12, p. 73; 13, p. 145; 14, p. 276; 15, p. 232]

Analysis of table 1 demonstrates that the dynamics of consumer demand in the hotel business are shaped by a complex combination of macroeconomic, socio-psychological, specific, and market factors, each of which, in its own way, determines the need for flexible pricing and guest length-of-stay management.

Macroeconomic changes, such as fluctuations in the incomes of the population or inflationary processes, directly affect consumers' purchasing power and willingness to book services, necessitating adjustments to tariff policies and the application of promotions [12, p. 73]. In parallel, economic policy and the broader economic environment shape customer expectations for service costs and availability, requiring enterprises to adopt a dynamic approach to managing demand and resources.

Social and psychological factors, including changing consumer preferences, fashion trends, and demographic transformations, affect market segmentation and require the adaptation of service packages and marketing strategies [13, p. 145]. The psychological state of the market, as manifested in the dominance of panic or euphoria, determines the pace of bookings and cancellations, which directly affects operational planning for tariffs and policies on minimum and maximum length of stay.

Specific factors, including seasonal fluctuations, geopolitical events, technological innovations and regulatory changes, change consumer expectations and their booking decisions. Such changes create the need for constant adaptation of pricing strategies and for the integration of new services into enterprises' offers [14, p. 276].

Market and price factors, including the ratio of demand to supply, the prices of related goods, and the liquidity of assets, directly determine the volume of sales and the level of income. Their influence is manifested in the need to adjust tariffs, introduce promotional offers, or regulate room availability, which allows maintaining a balance between maximizing revenue and the efficient use of resources [15, p. 232].

In general, the table demonstrates that the development of effective flexible pricing strategies and length-of-stay management is the result of an integrated approach that considers the interactions among all groups of factors and enables enterprises to adapt their operational decisions to changing market conditions.

Pricing strategies determine the company's approaches to forming the cost of goods and services in order to maximize revenue, attract customers and maintain competitiveness. In the modern business environment, both classical models and innovative approaches are used that take into account consumer behavior, market conditions and product features. The main types of pricing strategies and their key characteristics are presented below (table 2).

Table 2

Pricing strategies

Strategy type	Characteristics	Scope of application and effect
«Price skimming»	Setting high prices at the initial stage, when the offer is new and competition is limited	Maximizing profits from early adopters, suitable for new or premium services; gradually lowering prices as competition increases
Market penetration	Setting low prices to quickly capture market share	Attracting mass consumers, quickly expanding market share, using promotions for new customers
Prestige prices	Setting very high prices to create a luxury image	Focusing on wealthy customers, building a premium brand; minimal discounts, emphasis on quality and prestige
«Price leader»	Focusing on the pricing policy of the main competitor	Supporting competitive positioning in the market; price is set at or slightly below the market leader
Dynamic pricing	Price changes in real time depending on demand, seasonality and other factors	Optimization of revenue and occupancy; flexible prices with seasonal and situational adjustments
Market segmentation	Adaptation of tariffs for different categories of customers	Attracting different segments (business, tourists, corporate groups), increasing loyalty
Preferential prices	Providing discounts or special conditions for individual customer groups	Promoting sales and loyalty; applying bonuses, special packages
Cost orientation	Price is calculated based on cost plus desired profit	Profitability control and ensuring financial stability
Customer value orientation	Determining the price based on the customer's perceived benefit and service	Attracting customers who are willing to pay for specific benefits; focus on benefits, not just costs
Seasonal promotions and discounts	Temporary offers to stimulate demand	Increase occupancy in the low season; early booking, package deals

Source: author's own development [16, p. 5; 17, p. 3; 18, p. 5; 19, p. 158]

Modern approaches to pricing in the hotel business are based on adaptability and differentiation of tariffs according to the needs of different customer segments. This allows to adjust prices during peak and low periods, quickly respond to demand fluctuations driven by economic, socio-psychological, and regulatory factors, and manage income and occupancy of accommodation facilities more effectively. The use of special offers, package rates, and flexible conditions of stay helps stimulate demand during unstable periods and allows enterprises to maintain a balance between profitability and room occupancy.

Research on dynamic pricing and length-of-stay management enables assessment of the effectiveness of various strategies, integration into the overall revenue management policy, and adaptation of operational processes of hospitality enterprises to high-demand volatility. In this context, pricing is a key tool for strategic management of the enterprise, as it shapes the economic attractiveness of the offer across different market segments and determines the business's ability to respond to rapidly changing market conditions [16, p. 74].

The choice of an appropriate strategy should be made with the company's goals, product characteristics, and consumer behavior in mind. For example, the «skimming» strategy involves setting high prices for new products, which allows to maximize profit from early adopters while maintaining the uniqueness of the offer at the initial stage, especially for innovative products or premium services [17]. On the contrary, the market penetration strategy aims to set low prices to quickly gain significant market share, which is effective for mass products, attracting new customers and stimulating sales growth.

The prestige pricing strategy is based on high tariffs without discounts and emphasizes the product's quality and exclusivity, targeting wealthy consumers who value status and prestige. At the same time, the «price leader» strategy focuses on the prices set by the leading competitor, allowing to maintain competitiveness and retain existing customer base [18].

Dynamic pricing enables real-time tariff adjustments based on demand, helping maximize revenue and optimize load, especially for seasonal goods and services. Market segmentation allows to adapt prices for different groups of consumers, increasing their loyalty and interest in the offer, for example, through differentiation of tariffs for business clients and corporate groups. Preferential prices and special conditions stimulate sales, maintain relationships with regular customers, and attract new customers.

Thus, the pricing policy of hotel business enterprises is determined by the chosen strategic approach. In the case of cost orientation, the cost of services and the desire to ensure a certain level of profit are taken into account, while in the case of value orientation for the client, the emphasis is on the perceived benefit, the level of service and the willingness of consumers to pay for additional services and a high-quality product. To support demand during periods of low occupancy, special offers and flexible tariff packages are used, which stimulate bookings, attract new customer segments, and, at the same time, ensure the enterprise's financial stability and efficiency [19, p. 158].

In hotel business management, the key is using tools that enable rapid adaptation to changes in demand. Adjusting the length of stay of guests allows to optimize the occupancy of the room stock: limiting the minimum duration of booking contributes to an even distribution of customer flows during peak periods and reduces the risk of downtime, while controlling the maximum duration of stay ensures a balance between income and room availability, preventing the blocking of resources by long-term bookings during periods of high demand. The combined use of minimum and maximum restrictions creates optimal conditions for different categories of guests and allows to adapt offers to market dynamics, thereby increasing the efficiency of resource use [20].

The introduction of dynamic adjustment of booking rules through automated systems enables real-time, flexible management that accounts for occupancy and seasonal fluctuations. Such an integrated approach contributes to the simultaneous

preservation of the enterprise's competitiveness, stabilization of income, and maximization of profit, ensuring the efficient use of resources in conditions of high demand volatility.

In this context, the development of practical recommendations for implementing flexible pricing strategies and length-of-stay management is significant, as it allows not only to optimize the utilization of the room fund but also to increase the competitiveness and financial stability of enterprises (table 3).

Table 3

Recommendations for flexible pricing and length of stay management in conditions of high demand volatility

Recommendation	Application description
Integration of automated pricing systems	Adjust rates in real time depending on demand, seasonality and room occupancy. Using analytics and predictive models for decision-making
Using minimum and maximum length of stay restrictions	Adjusting booking duration to optimize occupancy, avoid downtime and block resources with long-term bookings
Customer segmentation and tariff adaptation	Developing different tariff packages for different consumer groups (tourists, corporate clients, premium guests), taking into account their needs and behavior
Implementing automated reservation management systems	Using special software to automatically adjust tariffs and length of stay restrictions in real time
Conducting regular analysis of strategy effectiveness	Monitoring the results of implemented tools, assessing the impact on revenues and occupancy, adjusting the strategy when market conditions change

Source: author's own development

Managing the hotel business in conditions of high demand volatility requires implementing adaptive strategies that maximize profits and efficiently use resources. Dynamic pricing is an important mechanism that enables promptly adjusting tariffs in response to changes in demand, seasonal fluctuations, and room occupancy levels. The use of analytical tools and forecasting models enables hotels to make more informed decisions, enhance the adaptability of their revenue management systems, and respond more effectively to market fluctuations.

Adjusting guests' length of stay by setting minimum and maximum limits is another vital tool. This allows to optimize room stock occupancy, avoid downtime, and avoid blocking resources with long-term bookings. This approach maintains a balance between revenue and room availability, ensuring a quick response to changes in demand and increasing the hotel's financial sustainability.

Customer segmentation and adaptation of tariffs according to their needs also play an essential role in the management strategy. Developing different tariff packages for tourists, corporate clients, and premium guests allows increasing loyalty and satisfaction, which contributes to the stability of income and the strengthening of competitive positions in the market.

Automating reservation management processes with specialized software enables operational adaptability to market fluctuations. This reduces the risk of errors in manual management and maintains the hotel's competitiveness and income stability.

Regular analysis of the effectiveness of implemented strategies is an essential component of successful management. Monitoring the results allows assessing the impact of new tools on income and occupancy, as well as timely adjusting the strategy in a changing market. This increases the business's stability and ensures long-term profitability. Thus, an integrated approach to pricing and length-of-stay management creates the conditions for successful operations in a highly competitive environment.

Conclusions. The study systematically analyzed the factors that drive demand variability in the hotel sector and assessed their impact on the formulation of flexible pricing strategies and on guest length-of-stay management. It is found that macroeconomic conditions, socio-psychological trends, specific market circumstances and price factors are interrelated and form the complex dynamics of consumer demand. This emphasizes the need to apply adaptive approaches to decision-making that enable prompt responses to demand fluctuations, improve forecasting accuracy, and effectively use the available resources of hospitality

enterprises. The analysis of pricing strategies showed that integrating approaches such as dynamic pricing, market segmentation, and customer value orientation helps balance revenues and room occupancy. Practical tools for managing the minimum and maximum length of stay were also studied, which help avoid resource blockage from long-term bookings and ensure an even distribution of guest flow during peak periods. The developed recommendations for automated pricing and reservation management systems enable a flexible, real-time tariff policy, increasing the competitiveness and financial stability of hotel businesses. The systematic combination of demand analytics, customer segmentation, and length-of-stay restrictions ensures efficient resource use and stable revenues even in conditions of high market volatility.

The scientific novelty of the results lies in the comprehensive approach to analyzing the influence of heterogeneous factors on the dynamics of demand and in integrating them into the formation of flexible pricing strategies and length-of-stay management. For the first time, macroeconomic, socio-psychological, specific, and market factors have been systematically combined with dynamic pricing and length-of-stay limitation tools, allowing the creation of an adaptive model of hotel enterprise revenue management. The practical significance lies in developing recommendations that provide a prompt response to demand fluctuations and optimize resource use in real time.

Further research may focus on modeling relationships among different categories of factors, using artificial intelligence and machine learning algorithms to forecast demand and optimize tariff policy, and on adapting the proposed strategies to the specifics of different segments of the hotel market, including the premium and corporate segments. Of particular interest is integrating consumer behavioral models with digital reservation management platforms to improve decision accuracy and build sustainable customer loyalty.

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